

Automated Information Enrichment for a Better Search

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Abstract

Automated Information Enrichment for a Better Search Information Enrichment and a Better Search The process of adding the Metadata when uploading a digital object onto a repository is usually manual. This means that the user has to have already at hand the keywords and all the other information about the asset. This paper addresses the possibility of enriching the “manual metadata” by generating automated metadata using the cognitive services provided by technologies like IBM Watson platform. The cognitive computing services offered by IBM Watson automatically generate Semantic Data (including Linked Data) for text and other types of data.

Current Status

During the upload of a digital object into a repository, the Metadata is added to the object manually by the person uploading the file (researcher, project member, etc). Usually, the digital object will not be thoroughly described at upload time. Some Metadata is added, but in most cases will be poorly described.

There are potential drawbacks with this manual process:

- Incompleteness of Metadata
- Typos
- Object incorrectly classified

Text Analytics

This paper suggests the introduction of a Text Analytics automated process during the upload of the digital object.

For this example, I have used IBM Watson Analytics Services . There are plenty of similar services in the Marketplace which offer similar features.

IBM Watson

Watson offers text analytics services to categorize text by **Concept, Keywords and Entities**.

Example

In this example, I provide the Title and Description of a document to Watson, and Watson returns “Semantic Information” in form of Concepts, Entities, and Keywords - and more- related to the text I provided,

Zenodo id

<https://zenodo.org/record/44893?n=en#.Vv61h2R95QI>

Keywords in Zenodo for this asset (added manually by the uploader of this file)

- Work-life balance
- Work-life balance model
- Work-life spheres
- Work-life segments
- Work-life balance benefits

Watson Results

I provide the text of the Title and Description to Watson. Below are the results from Watson.

Keywords computed by Watson:

Entities	Concept	Relevance	Linked Data
Keywords	21st century	0.952892	dbpedia freebase yago
Taxonomy			
Concepts	Recession	0.723387	dbpedia freebase yago
Document Sentiment			
Targeted Sentiment	20th century	0.718918	dbpedia freebase yago
Document Emotions (Beta)	Present	0.709028	dbpedia freebase
Relations			
Language	Unemployment	0.699621	dbpedia freebase webata
Title			
Author	Modern history	0.691225	dbpedia freebase yago
Text			
Feeds	Time	0.654916	dbpedia freebase
Microformats	Health	0.628727	dbpedia freebase webata

Entity	Relevance	Sentiment	Type	Subtypes	Linked Data
economic downturn	0.933285	mixed	FieldTerminology		

Concepts computed by Watson (including Linked Data):

Entity	Relevance	Sentiment	Type	Subtypes	Linked Data
economic downturn	0.933285	mixed	FieldTerminology		

Entities computed by Watson (also with Linked Data):

[Click here to learn more about entities.](#) Visual JSON API

Entity	Relevance	Sentiment	Type	Subtypes	Linked Data
economic downturn	0.933285	mixed	FieldTerminology		

Sentiments computed by Watson:

Entities	Target	Type
Keywords	economic downturn	Entity
Taxonomy	work-life balance	Keyword
Concepts	work-life balance discourse	Keyword
Document Sentiment	work-life balance facilities	Keyword
Targeted Sentiment	work-life balance programmes	Keyword
Document Emotions (Beta)	work-life balance initiatives	Keyword
Relations	healthy balance	Keyword
Language	economic downturn	Keyword
Title	current economic downturn	Keyword
Author	20th century	Keyword
Text	present economic downturn	Keyword
Feeds	early communal living	Keyword
Microformats	macro level model	Keyword
	conflicting demands	Keyword
	work demands	Keyword
	faster pace	Keyword
	late eighties	Keyword
	phenomenal growth	Keyword
	personal time	Keyword
	personal life	Keyword
	21st century	Keyword
	organisational level	Keyword
	cost cutting	Keyword
	present day theories	Keyword
	employees	Keyword
	need	Keyword
	relevance	Keyword

Relations computed by Watson:

Entities	This growth been abruptly interrupted by the current economic downturn			
Keywords	by the current economic downturn interrupted This growth			
Taxonomy	Extracted Sentence			
Concepts	This growth has been abruptly interrupted by the current economic downturn.			
Document Sentiment	Targeted Sentiment			
Document Emotions (Beta)	Parts of Speech			
Relations	Text	Speech Part	Sentiment	Keywords
Language	by the current economic downturn	subject	negative (relational)	current economic downturn
Title	interrupted	action		
Author	This growth	object	positive (relational), negative (directional)	growth
Text	Verb Normalization			
Feeds	Text	Lemma/ized	Verb	Tense
Microformats	interrupted	interrupt	interrupt	past
	Relational Entities			
	Entity	Speech Part	Type	Subtypes
	economic downturn	subject	Field/Terminology	

A Better Search

The results from Watson can make the search of digital objects more flexible.

The Search function can provide the ability to search on what it was **manually entered** as "Metadata" (Keywords, Tags, etc) by the uploader of the file, and also to **"semantically"** search using the **categorization** provided by Watson.

